

1 **On the Feasibility of Using Behavioral Listening Effort Test Methods to Evaluate Auditory**
2 **Performance in Cochlear Implant Users**

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4 Maartje M. E. Hendrikse¹, Gertjan Dingemanse¹, and André Goedegebure¹

5 ¹Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery, Erasmus Medical
6 Center, Rotterdam, the Netherlands.

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10 **Corresponding author:**

11 Maartje M. E. Hendrikse, Erasmus Medical Center, Department of ENT, Room Nt-310, P.O.

12 Box 2040, 3000 CA Rotterdam, the Netherlands. E-mail: m.hendrikse@erasmusmc.nl

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14

Abstract

15 Realistic outcome measures reflecting everyday hearing challenges are needed to evalu-
16 ate hearing aid and cochlear implant (CI) fitting. According to the literature, listening effort
17 measures may be more sensitive to differences between hearing-device settings than established
18 speech intelligibility measures. However, it is currently unclear which method to measure listen-
19 ing effort works best. The current study aimed to investigate the feasibility of two tests to meas-
20 ure changes in listening effort due to signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) differences, as would arise from
21 different hearing-device settings, in CI users. To evaluate the applicability of these tests in clini-
22 cal practice, the effect size of the SNR difference on the listening effort measures was compared
23 to the test-retest differences. A group of 19 CI users performed two listening effort tests at two
24 SNRs: +4 dB and +8 dB above their 50% speech perception threshold. Two behavioral tests with
25 a dual-task paradigm were used: a sentence final word identification and recall test (SWIRT) and
26 a sentence verification test (SVT). Both SVT and SWIRT were able to measure a significant dif-
27 ference in listening effort between the two SNR conditions, but the effect size was similar to the
28 test-retest difference, and the sensitivity was not better than that of speech intelligibility
29 measures. This makes SVT and SWIRT unsuitable for measuring listening effort differences of
30 this size in individual CI users, and therefore unsuitable for the evaluation of CI settings in the
31 clinic. However, SVT and SWIRT are suitable for research with CI users, when group data can
32 be analyzed.

33

34 **Keywords:** Speech Intelligibility, Dual Task, Test-Retest Reliability, Clinical Use

35

Introduction

36 Currently, hearing loss and aided performance are usually defined by pure-tone audiome-
37 try and speech intelligibility tests in the clinic. Whereas these objective measures can be very
38 sensitive when measuring specific hearing functions, they have limited ecological validity as
39 they use strictly controlled stimuli that are different from sounds and speech in daily life. They
40 also only have a moderate correlation with self-perceived handicap (e.g., Chang, Ho, & Chou,
41 2009). Pure-tone thresholds and speech intelligibility measures thus appear to be limited in pre-
42 dicting the consequences that hearing loss has on a person's daily activities (Granberg et al.,
43 2014). Moreover, speech intelligibility tests are not particularly sensitive to differences in gain-
44 frequency response shape for different hearing-aid settings (Smeds, Dahlquist, Larsson, Herrlin,
45 & Wolters, 2019).

46 In the study of Granberg et al. (2014), many participants reported that it required signifi-
47 cant effort to listen and simultaneously perform necessary mental functions involved in commu-
48 nication such as concentrating, shifting and dividing attention between stimuli. Quantifying this
49 effort required for listening is another approach to evaluating hearing impairment and aided per-
50 formance, and has received considerable attention in the scientific community in recent years. In
51 scientific literature, listening effort is defined as *the deliberate allocation of cognitive resources*
52 *to overcome obstacles or challenges to achieving listening-oriented goals* (Francis & Love,
53 2020; Pichora-Fuller et al., 2016). Hearing impairment is known to be one of those obstacles, so
54 hearing-impaired listeners have to allocate more cognitive resources (selective attention, working
55 memory) to make sense of a signal in a complex acoustic environment than normal-hearing lis-
56 teners (Shinn-Cunningham & Best, 2008). Moreover, it is known that cognitive resources have a

57 limited capacity (Kahneman, 1973), so when listening is more effortful, fewer cognitive re-
58 sources are left for higher-level processing of auditory information (Lunner et al., 2020). Francis
59 & Love (2003; 2020) make a distinction between the effort that is demanded by the listening sit-
60 uation (*demanded effort*), the effort that a listener actually exerts in that situation (*exerted effort*),
61 and the feelings that a listener has about how much effort is being spent (*assessed effort*). A
62 measure of exerted listening effort may be a better indicator of aided performance in challenging
63 situations compared to speech intelligibility, because it reflects the use of cognitive resources
64 needed to perform a task, rather than just the task performance. In addition, listening effort
65 measures may be more sensitive at high intelligibility levels where speech intelligibility
66 measures are less sensitive, because of the different amount of cognitive resources it may take to
67 achieve similar intelligibility. Timmer et al. (2018) showed that when mildly hearing-impaired
68 listeners were provided with hearing aids, this had a larger effect on their listening effort ratings
69 than on their speech understanding ratings. The same may apply for listeners with more severe
70 hearing loss, when provided with new hearing devices or hearing-device settings. Therefore, lis-
71 tening effort could be a more powerful measure to evaluate differences between hearing-device
72 settings than speech intelligibility.

73 Approaches to measure exerted listening effort can be behavioral methods or physiologi-
74 cal methods. Behavioral methods typically involve a dual-task paradigm. The primary task in-
75 volves word or sentence recognition, and according to a systematic review of Ohlenforst et al.
76 (2017), the secondary task can use different measures (accuracy, recall, reaction time) and in-
77 volve different modalities (auditory, visual, tactile). There does not seem to be a consensus in the
78 literature on the nature of the secondary task (Gagne, Besser, & Lemke, 2017). As the primary

79 task demands more listening effort, fewer cognitive resources are available to perform the sec-
80 ondary task, thus task performance decreases. Finally, examples of physiological methods are
81 functional magnetic resonance imaging, pupillometry, or electroencephalographic response
82 measurements during listening task performance (Ohlenforst et al., 2017).

83 Ohlenforst et al. (2017) concluded that studies investigating whether hearing-aid amplifi-
84 cation reduced listening effort reported mixed results, and that there were large differences in
85 study design and test methods. This is also true for studies comparing different hearing-device
86 settings, for example different noise reduction algorithms. Desjardins & Doherty (2014) found a
87 significant decrease in listening effort because of noise reduction in hearing-aid users during a
88 dual-task paradigm measuring speech intelligibility and visual tracking. Furthermore, Lunner et
89 al. (2016; Ng, Rudner, Lunner, Pedersen, & Ronnberg, 2013) were able to identify benefits from
90 HA signal processing using a dual-task paradigm measuring speech intelligibility and memory
91 recall for the last word in a sentence. Moreover, Pals et al. (2020) were able to detect differences
92 in speech comprehension and listening effort with a different number of active electrodes in CI
93 users (7 versus 15), using a dual-task paradigm measuring the ability and reaction time to clas-
94 sify sentences as true or false. On the other hand, Brons et al. (2013) found no significant reduc-
95 tion in subjective listening effort ratings when turning on different noise reduction algorithms for
96 simulations in normal-hearing listeners. Finally, Dingemanse & Goedegebure (2022) found no
97 reduction in listening effort when turning on a noise reduction algorithm in CI users using pupil-
98 lometry. Currently, there is no consensus on which method is best suited to measure listening ef-
99 fort. An effective method must be sufficiently sensitive to be able to measure differences in lis-
100 tening effort due to different hearing-device settings, and must also be applicable to individuals

101 in clinical settings. To reach a consensus on which test methods are most suitable, it is necessary
102 to compare different methods within the same population and in the same conditions.

103 The current study aims to investigate the feasibility of using behavioral listening effort
104 tests to measure listening effort in CI users, with the ultimate purpose of assessing the feasibility
105 to evaluate different hearing-device settings in the clinic. Moreover, a comparison with speech
106 intelligibility measures was made, to check the assumption that listening effort measures are
107 more sensitive than speech intelligibility measures at high intelligibility levels. Behavioral listen-
108 ing effort test methods were chosen, because these methods are likely better suited for use in the
109 clinic. Two behavioral listening effort test methods were compared: a speech recall test (Lunner
110 et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2013), referred to as the sentence-final word identification and recall task
111 (SWIRT); a sentence verification task (SVT) paradigm (Baddeley, Emslie, & Nimmo-Smith,
112 1992; May, Alcock, Robinson, & Mwita, 2001), of which a Dutch corpus is available (Adank &
113 Janse, 2009; Janse & Adank, 2012). These test methods have shown promising results in measur-
114 ing listening effort in hearing-device users (Lunner et al., 2016; Ng et al., 2013; Pals et al.,
115 2020). Both test methods use a dual-task paradigm, which results in a measure of speech intelli-
116 gibility and a measure of listening effort. The study was conducted with a group of CI users since
117 it is more difficult to measure differences in listening effort in this group. Perreau et al. (2017)
118 have shown that when comparing more and less favorable SNR conditions, listening effort was
119 reduced to a greater degree for normal-hearing listeners compared to CI users. Thus, the differ-
120 ences in listening effort between more and less favorable SNR conditions that occur in CI users
121 are smaller, and therefore more difficult to measure. The two behavioral listening effort tests
122 were conducted in two SNR conditions slightly below peak intelligibility performance. For the
123 listening effort tests to be feasible, they should be able to measure a difference in listening effort

124 between the SNR conditions. For clinical use, the measured difference between the SNR condi-
125 tions should be larger than the test-retest difference, so that conclusions can be drawn based on
126 individual measurements rather than group data. Furthermore, if listening effort measures are
127 more sensitive, we expect the effect of the SNR condition on the listening effort measures to be
128 larger than on the speech intelligibility measures.

129 **Method**

130 **Participants**

131 CI users (12 male, 7 female) aged between 29 and 79 years (mean: 63.6 years) were in-
132 cluded in the study. All participants had a post-lingual onset of hearing loss and were implanted
133 more than 6 months before the test. Participants had no known cognitive disabilities and had a
134 phoneme score of at least 65% at 65 dB on clinically used Dutch consonant-vowel-consonant
135 word lists. This should correspond to a word score of >70% for sentences in quiet (Dingemans
136 & Goedegebure, 2019b), so that a reliable measurement of the 50% intelligibility threshold
137 would be possible for sentences in noise (Dingemans & Goedegebure, 2019a). One participant
138 did not reach 70% intelligibility in quiet for the sentences used in the test and was excluded be-
139 cause the tests were too difficult. The data of the remaining 18 participants were included in the
140 analysis. Participants signed a written informed consent form. The study protocol has been sub-
141 mitted to the Erasmus Medical Center Ethics Committee under the number MEC-2021-0764 and
142 deemed exempt from review.

143 **Procedure**

144 First, the 50% Speech Reception Threshold (SRT50) measurements were conducted as
145 described in the following to determine the SNR values for the two conditions at SRT50 +4 dB
146 and +8 dB. Next, SWIRT and SVT were conducted in the two SNR conditions as described in

147 the following. A retest was done for SWIRT and SVT in both SNR conditions in a separate ses-
148 sion approximately one week later with the same participants. The test items and lists were cho-
149 sen randomly. The SNR conditions were counterbalanced across participants, and the order of
150 SWIRT and SVT was also counterbalanced.

151 For CI users, the intelligibility for the VU sentences varies strongly between individuals
152 (Dingemanse & Goedegebure, 2020; see Figure 1). As shown in Figure 1, many CI users are not
153 able to reach 100% of words correct, even in quiet. Therefore, it was not feasible to pick an SNR
154 where a certain percentage of word recognition was achieved (85% or 95% in previous studies
155 using SWIRT; Ng et al., 2013; Ng, Rudner, Lunner, & Ronnberg, 2015). Instead, the SNR condi-
156 tions were chosen relative to the measured SRT50, in the SNR region where the slope of the psy-
157 chometric curve is flattening (slightly below every individual's maximum intelligibility). In this
158 SNR region speech intelligibility measures are less sensitive than around SRT50, and listening
159 effort measures are believed to be more informative. A small difference in speech intelligibility
160 between the SNR conditions was necessary to ensure that there was a difference in listening ef-
161 fort, because another study with CI users did not measure a difference in listening effort between
162 SNRs where the speech perception score was at its maximum (Perreau et al., 2017). In addition
163 to measuring at relatively high intelligibility with a difference in listening effort between the two
164 conditions, we wanted to ensure that the SNR difference reflected a difference that could result
165 from different hearing-device settings. Differences in SNR resulting from different hearing-de-
166 vice settings, for example, noise reduction algorithms, are typically a few dB, on average 2.5 dB
167 for the four algorithms in the study of Brons et al. (2013) with a maximum of 7 dB for the most
168 effective algorithm. In the current study, a difference of 4 dB between conditions was chosen,
169 which is realistic for an effective noise reduction algorithm.

170

171 *Figure 1: Psychometric curves for normal-hearing listeners (NH) and four groups of cochlear-implant (CI) users with different*
 172 *50% speech reception thresholds (SRT50) according to Dingemanse & Goedegebure (2020). The SRT50, SRT50+4 dB, and*
 173 *SRT50+8 dB points are indicated, to show where they lie on the psychometric curve.*

174 **SRT50 measurement**

175 Speech intelligibility was measured with the Dutch VU (Vrije Universiteit) sentence test
 176 spoken by a native Dutch female speaker (Versfeld, Daalder, Festen, & Houtgast, 2000). The
 177 sentences are unrelated with a length of five to nine words (median length of six words) and
 178 were selected from newspaper databases.

179 First, a training list was presented in quiet to allow participants to get familiar with the
 180 test and material. If the word score in quiet was less than 70%, the participant was excluded from
 181 further tests. Participants had to repeat the words that they understood after each sentence. The
 182 presentation level of the sentences was fixed at 70 dB (SPL), and they were presented from a
 183 loudspeaker placed in the frontal direction. The sentences were presented in coincident steady-
 184 state speech-spectrum noise matching the female speaker, the level of which was adapted to
 185 reach a word score of 50% correct. As an adaptive procedure, a stochastic approximation method
 186 with SNR step size $4 \cdot (50\% - Pc(n - 1))$ (Dingemanse & Goedegebure, 2019a; Robbins &
 187 Monro, 1951) was used, with $Pc(n - 1)$ being the percentage correctly repeated words of the
 188 previous sentence. An initial SNR value of +2 dB was used. Two lists of 13 sentences were used

189 to determine the SRT50, which is defined as the average SNR over sentences 5 to 27, where the
190 27th level is calculated from the adaptive formula based on the word score from the 26th sentence.

191 The SRT50 was also measured with the speech material from SVT. Because this material
192 is spoken by a male speaker instead of a female speaker and the structure of the sentences is dif-
193 ferent, the SRT50 is likely different. Different steady-state speech spectrum noise was used that
194 matches the male speaker of the SVT material. Only true sentences were used for the SRT50
195 measurement. The number of sentences and the adaptive procedure were equal to that used for
196 the SRT50 measurement of the VU sentences.

197 The SNR conditions (SRT50 + 4 dB and SRT50 + 8 dB) for SWIRT were based on the
198 SRT50 score with the VU sentences, and the SNR conditions for SVT were based on the SRT50
199 score with the SVT material.

200 **Sentence verification test (SVT)**

201 Dutch true or false sentences were used, spoken by a native Dutch male speaker, and rec-
202 orded by Adank & Janse (Adank & Janse, 2009; Janse & Adank, 2012). A total of 100 sentences
203 contained a true statement (e.g., *Tomaten groeien aan planten*, Tomatoes grow on plants), and
204 100 contained a false or nonsense statement (e.g., *Tomaten hebben sterke tanden*, Tomatoes have
205 strong teeth). False sentences were created by combining a subject noun from one sentence with
206 a non-matching predicate from a different sentence. Thus the sentences can be regarded as pairs
207 that have the same predicate, and either a matching or non-matching noun. Five sentence pairs
208 were excluded as we did not think they were unarguably true/false, leaving 95 pairs. Participants
209 were instructed to listen to a sentence and indicate whether the sentence was true or false by
210 pressing a green or red button on a touch screen as accurately and fast as possible (it was allowed
211 to respond before the end of the sentence). The first response given between 0.8 s before and 3.0

212 s after the end of the sentence counted. Sentences were presented at 70 dB (SPL) in coincident
213 steady-state speech-spectrum noise matching the male speaker of the sentence material. The re-
214 sponse and reaction time relative to the end of the sentence (negative when the response was be-
215 fore the end of the sentence) were logged. A training was done with 10 sentences (five true, five
216 false) to familiarize the participants with the task. A total of 30 sentences (15 true, 15 false) were
217 measured per condition. A silent interval with a 3.0 s duration was used between the end of a
218 sentence and the presentation of the next sentence to give participants time to respond. If no re-
219 sponse was given within 3.0 s, this was logged as a missing response. The two test outcomes
220 were the reaction time and the proportion of correctly classified sentences.

221 **Speech recall test (SWIRT)**

222 Dutch VU sentences (Versfeld et al., 2000) ending in two- or three-syllable words were
223 used as stimuli. Lists of seven sentences were created for SWIRT, by extracting the first seven
224 sentences that ended in two- or three-syllable words from each VU list of 13 sentences. Thus the
225 sentences from one VU list were kept together, as they were sorted based on phonological con-
226 tent (Versfeld et al., 2000), and to make sure to select different sentences from the sentences
227 used in the SRT50 measurement. Four lists (out of 39) contained less than seven sentences with
228 two- or three-syllable last words and are thus not used for SWIRT. The sentences were presented
229 at 70 dB (SPL) in coincident steady-state speech-spectrum noise matching the female speaker.
230 Lunner et al. (2020) suggested varying the task difficulty so that it better matches the individual
231 cognitive capacity. Therefore, the appropriate list length (either five or seven sentences) was se-
232 lected based on the task performance with a training list of five sentences. If participants were
233 able to recall 0-4 words, SWIRT was conducted with a list length of five sentences, if they re-
234 called 5 words correctly, SWIRT was conducted with a list length of seven sentences. Five lists

235 were measured in each SNR condition. The participants had to repeat the final word after every
236 sentence, and after the entire list was presented, they had to recall as many of the final words as
237 possible, in any order. If a final word was repeated incorrectly, but the incorrectly repeated word
238 was recalled, this was counted as a correct recall. If the final word was not understood at all, par-
239 ticipants were instructed to name and remember a different word, so that reduced intelligibility
240 would not influence the recall performance. The two outcomes were the proportion of correctly
241 recalled words and the proportion of correctly repeated words.

242 **Setup**

243 Sentences and background noise were presented over a single Genelec 8020 loudspeaker
244 placed 1.13 m in front of the participant at ear level inside a sound booth. The loudspeaker was
245 connected to a Focusrite Scarlett Solo 3rd Gen USB audio interface located outside the sound
246 booth, which was controlled by a PC running TASCAR version 0.222 (Grimm, Luberadzka, &
247 Hohmann, 2019) and MATLAB R2021a. For SWIRT and SRT50 measurements, responses were
248 entered manually by the experimenter in a MATLAB GUI. For SVT, participants touched the
249 corresponding true/false button on an interface on an Android smartphone. The interface was de-
250 signed using the TouchOSC app and sent an Open Sound Control (OSC) message to the TAS-
251 CAR data logging when a button was pressed or released. Button press events were stored in the
252 data logging with a constant low latency of less than 40 ms (SD <23 ms).

253

254 **Analyses**

255 First, the SRT50 scores with the VU sentences (used in SWIRT) and the SVT sentences
256 were compared to check for potential differences in intelligibility between the speech materials.
257 The SRT50 scores were not normally distributed, so a Wilcoxon signed rank test was done for

258 the SRT50 scores per participant for both speech materials to check for significant differences.
259 Since the scores with both speech materials are a measure of SRT50 we expected a significant
260 correlation between the scores, and the Spearman correlation coefficient was calculated to con-
261 firm this.

262 Next, it was analyzed for both SVT and SWIRT whether some items/lists can be consid-
263 ered outliers because of statistically different scores for that item/list. For the outlier analysis, for
264 each study variable an appropriate distribution (see next paragraph) was fitted to all trials meas-
265 ured in the most difficult (SRT50 + 4 dB) condition. Then, for each item/list the probability that
266 the mean score for that item/list came from the fitted distribution was calculated. If that probabil-
267 ity was < 1%, the item/list was considered an outlier. Trials with items/lists that were identified
268 as outliers were removed from further analyses.

269 The primary study variables are the two listening-effort-related measures: the proportion
270 of correctly recalled last words from the sentence after presentation of the entire list in SWIRT
271 and the reaction time when categorizing sentences as true/false in SVT. The secondary study var-
272 iables are the two speech-intelligibility-related measures: the proportion of correctly repeated last
273 words after presentation of the sentence in SWIRT and the proportion of sentences categorized
274 correctly as true/false in SVT. For SVT, some trials were missing because participants did not
275 respond within 3 s after the end of the sentence (2.2% of the trials). Binomial distributions were
276 used to fit the proportion of correctly repeated and recalled words in SWIRT and the proportion
277 of correctly categorized sentences in SVT, because of the binary nature of the response to each
278 trial (correct or incorrect). As can be seen in Figure 4A, the distribution for the reaction times in
279 SVT is positively skewed, so not normally distributed. We chose to fit a Gamma distribution to
280 the reaction time data, in accordance with literature (Baayen & Milin, 2010) and as was done in

281 several other recent studies that used reaction time as a measure of listening effort (e.g., Lee &
282 Lee, 2022; Prodi, Visentin, Borella, Mammarella, & Di Domenico, 2021; Visentin et al., 2022).
283 Note that we had to shift the reaction time data by 0.8 s to make it all positive values, as the
284 Gamma distribution does not allow negative values. This way, 0 s corresponded to the earliest
285 possible response that counted, and 0.8 s corresponded to the end of the sentence.

286 The data were analyzed using generalized linear mixed-effects models (GLMMs), which
287 can handle non-normally distributed variables and missing data points. GLMMs are increasingly
288 used in hearing science in recent years (e.g., Lee & Lee, 2022; Prodi et al., 2021), and are be-
289 lieved to be a superior analysis method compared to ANOVA (Jaeger, 2008; Quené & van den
290 Bergh, 2008). GLMMs were fitted in R (version 4.2.2; R_Core_Team, 2023) using the Laplace
291 approximation procedure with the ‘lme4’ package (version 1.1.31; Bates, Mächler, Bolker, &
292 Walker, 2015), and described using the ‘report’ package (version 0.5.5; Makowski, Ben-Shachar,
293 Patil, & Lüdecke, 2020). The R scripts used for the analysis can be found in the accompanying
294 dataset (Hendrikse, Dingemanse, & Goedegebure, 2022). A GLMM was fitted for each of the
295 study variables. First, it was determined which random effects (participant and/or item/list)
296 should be added to the GLMM by comparing a baseline intercept-only GLM to GLMMs with
297 random intercepts using Chi-square difference tests. Secondly, a full GLMM was fitted for each
298 study variable, including the SNR condition and test/retest condition as fixed effects, and random
299 slopes for the SNR condition per participant and/or per item/list. Because the slope of the psy-
300 chometric curve may differ between participants (see Figure 1) and the difficulty may differ be-
301 tween items/lists, the effect of the SNR condition may differ as well and random slopes were
302 added. In case the model did not converge, the random slopes per participant and/or per item/list
303 were removed. Additional potentially relevant fixed effects were included in the full model as

304 described in the results section. Then, the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC; Akaike, 1973) was
305 used to select the best model by removing the random slopes and additional fixed effects one by
306 one and determining whether that improved the model fit. Furthermore, interactions for the re-
307 maining fixed factors were added to see whether this would further improve the model fit, and
308 significant interactions were reported separately. Finally, the standardized coefficients were ob-
309 tained by refitting the best model on a standardized version of the dataset. The 95% Confidence
310 Intervals (C.I.s) and p-values for the standardized coefficients were computed using a Wald t- or
311 z-distribution approximation. The standardized coefficient for the SNR condition can be re-
312 garded as a kind of effect size and showed how well the study variables could differentiate be-
313 tween the SNR conditions and thus how sensitive each test method was to SNR differences. This
314 was compared to the standardized coefficient for the test/retest condition, showing how accurate
315 each test method was.

316

317

Results

318 **SRT50 scores**

319 The mean SRT50 scores and standard deviations were 3.1 ± 2.9 dB for the VU sentences
320 and 4.2 ± 3.2 dB for the SVT sentences (Figure 2). As expected, the SRT50 scores for the two
321 speech materials were significantly correlated with a Spearman correlation coefficient of 0.74 (p
322 $< .001$). This persisted when the most outlying participant with high SRT50 scores was removed
323 (Spearman correlation coefficient 0.69, $p = 0.0027$). According to Dingemans & Goedegebure
324 (2019a), the test-retest standard deviation of CI users for the VU sentences is 2.4 dB, and a sig-
325 nificant individual difference at the .05 level would require an SNR difference of 4.7 dB. As can
326 be seen in Figure 2, for none of the participants the difference between the SRT50 scores was

327 larger than the value of 4.7 dB. On group level, a Wilcoxon signed rank test did reveal a signifi-
 328 cant difference between the SRT50 scores for the VU and SVT sentences (z-value = -2.72; two-
 329 sided $p = 0.006$), indicating slightly better intelligibility for the VU sentences.

330

331 *Figure 2: Scatter plot with SRT50 scores for all participants for the VU sentences and SVT sentences. The grey area indicates the*
 332 *± 4.7 dB test-retest 95% confidence interval of the VU sentences.*

333 **Outliers in test items**

334 For the proportion of trials answered correctly in SVT, several items with a low mean
 335 score were identified for which the probability was $< 1\%$ than the mean for that item resulted
 336 from the binomial distribution fitted to all trials in the most difficult SNR condition (Figure 3).
 337 The labeled items in Figure 3 (9 in total) are considered outliers. The sentences associated with
 338 these item numbers can be found in the accompanying data set. The trials with the items that
 339 were identified as outliers are removed in further analyses. For the other three study variables, no
 340 outliers were identified.

341

342 *Figure 3: Proportion of trials answered correctly for each item in SVT. For each item, the 99%-confidence interval is plotted for*
 343 *a binomial distribution using the fitted chance of success for all data points in the most difficult SNR condition, and the number*
 344 *of trials with that item. Items with means outside this confidence interval are considered outliers.*

345 **SVT and SWIRT scores**

346 The listening effort and speech intelligibility scores for SVT and SWIRT are plotted in

347 Figure 4.

348

349 *Figure 4: Combined boxplot and density plot of the listening effort (A, B) and speech intelligibility (C, D) measures for SVT (A,*
 350 *C) and SWIRT (B, D) tests. For the reaction time in SVT, data points for all trials are plotted (A) to show the distribution. The*
 351 *other measures have a binomial distribution, so data points for the mean per participant are plotted (B-D). In addition to the*

352 *data points, the interquartile range (black vertical line), median (white dot), and mean (black horizontal line) are plotted. The*
353 *mean value is also displayed.*

354 **SVT, listening effort**

355 We fitted a GLMM (Gamma family with log link, estimated using optimx optimizer) to analyze
356 the effect of SNR condition on the reaction time measured in SVT. The following additional
357 fixed effects were included in the full model: whether the item was true or false ('item type'), the
358 order of the SNR conditions ('order'), whether the item was categorized correctly ('answer'),
359 and the word score for the VU training list in quiet ('word score VU quiet'). Adding random in-
360 tercepts per list and per participant improved the model. The full model converged only without
361 random slopes for the SNR condition per participant (random slopes for the SNR condition per
362 item were included), and there was no overdispersion. After AIC-based model selection, the
363 model included the parameters listed in Table 1. The best model's total explanatory power is
364 substantial (conditional $R^2 = 0.34$) and the part related to the fixed effects alone (marginal R^2) is
365 0.15. Adding an interaction effect between SNR condition, test/retest, and order further improved
366 the model significantly ($\chi^2 = 33.87$, $p < .001$), and the interaction effect on the reaction time was
367 significant ($p < .001$; std. coefficient = 0.23, 95% C.I. [0.14, 0.32]).

368 The parameter estimates (Table 1) indicate a significant effect of SNR condition on reaction time
369 in SVT, but also a significant interaction with test/retest and order was found. Interpreting this
370 interaction, Figure 5 shows that in only 2 of the 4 combinations of test/retest and order, partici-
371 pants responded faster in the SRT50 + 8 dB condition than in the SRT50 + 4 dB condition. The
372 mean difference in reaction time per participant and between SNR conditions is on average 0.059
373 s. The mean difference in reaction time per participant between test and retest is larger: partici-
374 pants responded on average 0.113 s faster in the retest compared to the test. The standardized co-
375 efficients for the SNR condition and test/retest condition are similar in size (within each other's

376 95% C.I.), which indicates that the effect of the SNR condition on the listening effort measured
 377 with SVT was similar in size compared to the effect of test/retest.

378 *Table 1: Summary of fixed effects for the GLMM of reaction time in SVT.*

Parameter	Std. Coefficient	95% C.I.	p value
(Intercept)	0.63	[0.49, 0.78]	< .001 ***
SNR condition	0.04	[0.01, 0.08]	0.014 *
test/retest	-0.06	[-0.08, -0.04]	< .001 ***
order	0.16	[-0.03, 0.35]	0.101
answer	-0.21	[-0.25, -0.17]	< .001 ***
item type	-0.07	[-0.12, -0.01]	0.022 *
word score VU quiet	-0.05	[-0.14, 0.05]	0.342

< .05 *; < .01 **; < .001 ***

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381

382 *Figure 5: Median and interquartile range of reaction time in SVT per SNR condition, order, test, and retest.*

383 **SVT, speech intelligibility**

384 To analyze the effect of SNR condition on the answer given when categorizing the sentences in
 385 SVT, a GLMM (binomial family with logit link, estimated using bobyqa optimizer) was fitted.
 386 The full model included the same fixed effects as the GLMM for the reaction time outcome of
 387 the SVT, except for whether the trial was categorized correctly as true/false ('answer'), which
 388 was the dependent variable in this model. Adding random intercepts per list and per participant

389 improved the model. The full model converged only without random slopes for the SNR condi-
 390 tion per participant and per item, and there was no overdispersion. After AIC-based model selec-
 391 tion, the model included the parameters listed in Table 2. The best model's total explanatory
 392 power is moderate (conditional $R^2 = 0.17$) and the part related to the fixed effects alone (mar-
 393 ginal R^2) is 0.06.

394 The parameter estimates for the best model (Table 2) indicated a significant effect of 'word score
 395 VU quiet' and item type on the answer given in SVT, but there was no significant effect of SNR
 396 condition. This indicates that the SVT speech intelligibility measure was insensitive to the SNR
 397 difference. Investigating the effect of item type shows that on average more trials were answered
 398 correctly when the sentence was false (93.1%) compared to when the sentence was true (86.8%).
 399 Whereas 50% of the trials were true and 50% false, the participants categorized 52.0% of the tri-
 400 als as false, 45.7% as true, and did not respond in 2.3% of the trials. Finally, a better 'word score
 401 VU quiet' corresponded on average to a higher proportion of correctly answered trials in SVT.

402 *Table 2: Summary of fixed effects for the GLMM of answer in SVT.*

Parameter	Std. Coefficient	95% C.I.	p value
(Intercept)	3.03	[2.59, 3.48]	0.293
SNR condition	-0.15	[-0.47, 0.18]	0.384
test/retest	0.10	[-0.23, 0.42]	0.565
order	-0.03	[-0.38, 0.32]	0.872
item type	-0.72	[-1.11, -0.32]	< .001 ***
word score VU quiet	0.34	[0.19, 0.49]	< .001 ***

< .05 *; < .01 **; < .001 ***

403

404 **SWIRT, listening effort**

405 To analyze the effect of SNR condition on the listening effort measured with SWIRT, a GLMM
 406 (binomial family with logit link, estimated using bobyqa optimizer) was fitted. The full model

407 included the following additional fixed effects: the order of the SNR conditions ('order'), the po-
408 sition of the sentence in the list ('position in list'), whether the word type was a verb, noun, ad-
409 jective, or other ('word type'), and the word score for the VU training list in quiet ('word score
410 VU quiet'). The 'position in list' was included, because it is known that the last word from the
411 final sentence in the list is more easily recalled than the last words from the first and middle sen-
412 tences (Lunner et al., 2016). The 'word type' was included, because some participants mentioned
413 that the verbs were more alike and more difficult to remember and we wanted to investigate this.
414 Adding a random intercept per list did not improve the model, but adding a random intercept per
415 participant did improve the model. The full model converged only without random slopes for the
416 SNR condition per participant, and there was no overdispersion. After AIC-based model selec-
417 tion, the model included the parameters listed in Table 3. The best model's total explanatory
418 power is moderate (conditional $R^2 = 0.22$) and the part related to the fixed effects alone (mar-
419 ginal R^2) is 0.19.

420 The parameter estimates for the best model (Table 3) indicated a significant effect of SNR condi-
421 tion and position in list on the proportion of words recalled correctly. When looking at the mean
422 proportions of words recalled correctly per participant, we see that participants recalled on aver-
423 age 3.8% more words correctly in the SRT50 + 8 dB condition than in the SRT50 + 4 dB condi-
424 tion. The mean difference in proportion of words recalled correctly per participant between test
425 and retest is lower, on average 2.7%. The standardized coefficients for the SNR condition and
426 test/retest condition are similar in size (within each other's 95% C.I.), which indicates that the
427 effect of the SNR condition on the listening effort measured with SWIRT was similar in size
428 compared to the effect of test/retest. Moreover, a significant effect of 'position in list' was found,

429 because the last word in the list was significantly more often recalled (92.2%) than the first
 430 (64.4%) and middle (57.0%) words.

431 *Table 3: Summary of fixed effects for the GLMM of 'recalled' in SWIRT.*

Parameter		Std. Coefficient	95% C.I.	p value
(Intercept)		0.39	[-0.13, 0.90]	0.281
SNR condition		-0.20	[-0.39, 0.00]	0.049 *
test/retest		0.13	[-0.07, 0.33]	0.200
order		0.006	[-0.43, 0.44]	0.980
position in list (vs. first)	middle	-0.33	[-0.58, -0.08]	0.010 *
	last	1.92	[1.47, 2.37]	< .001 ***
word type (vs. adjective)	noun	0.40	[0.00, 0.80]	0.053
	other	-0.05	[-0.51, 0.41]	0.830
	verb	0.29	[-0.12, 0.70]	0.160
word score VU quiet		0.15	[-0.06, 0.36]	0.155

< .05 *; < .01 **; < .001 ***

432

433 **SWIRT, speech intelligibility**

434 Furthermore, a GLMM (binomial family with logit link, estimated using bobyqa opti-
 435 mizer) was fitted to analyze the effect of the SNR condition on the repeated last words in
 436 SWIRT. The full model included the same fixed effects as in the full model for the listening ef-
 437 fort with SWIRT. Adding random intercepts per list and per participant improved the model. The
 438 full model converged only without random slopes for the SNR condition per participant and per
 439 list, and there was no overdispersion. After AIC-based model selection, the best model included
 440 the parameters listed in Table 4. The best model's total explanatory power is moderate (condi-
 441 tional $R^2 = 0.20$) and the part related to the fixed effects alone (marginal R^2) is 0.12. Adding an
 442 interaction effect between SNR condition and 'word score VU quiet' further improved the model
 443 significantly ($\chi^2 = 6.90$, $p = 0.009$), and the interaction effect on the proportion of words repeated
 444 correctly was significant ($p = 0.008$; std. coefficient = -0.34, 95% C.I. [-0.59, -0.09]).

445 The final fit indicated a significant effect of SNR condition and ‘word score VU quiet’
 446 (Table 4). When looking at the mean proportions of words repeated correctly per participant, we
 447 see that participants repeated on average 11.6% more words correctly in the SRT50 + 8 dB con-
 448 dition than in the SRT50 + 4 dB condition. The mean difference in proportion of words repeated
 449 correctly per participant between test and retest is lower, on average 1.0%. The magnitude of the
 450 standardized coefficient for SNR condition is much larger than that of the coefficient for test/re-
 451 test condition. This indicates that the effect of the SNR condition on the speech intelligibility
 452 measured with SWIRT was larger than the effect of test/retest. Finally, a better ‘word score VU
 453 quiet’ resulted on average in a higher proportion of correctly repeated last words, and the interac-
 454 tion showed that the difference in proportion of correctly repeated last words between SNR con-
 455 ditions was larger for participants with a better ‘word score VU quiet’.

456 *Table 4: Summary of fixed effects for the GLMM of ‘repeated’ in SWIRT.*

Parameter		Std. Coefficient	95% C.I.	p value
(Intercept)		2.97	[2.22, 3.72]	0.956
SNR condition		-1.23	[-1.54, -0.92]	< .001 ***
test/retest		0.08	[-0.20, 0.36]	0.565
order		-0.16	[-0.59, 0.27]	0.474
position in list (vs. first)	middle	-0.25	[-0.63, 0.12]	0.188
	last	-0.08	[-0.56, 0.39]	0.733
word type (vs. adjective)	noun	-0.14	[-0.73, 0.45]	0.636
	other	-0.02	[-0.71, 0.67]	0.951
	verb	0.26	[-0.34, 0.87]	0.394
word score VU quiet		0.25	[0.05, 0.45]	0.012 *

< .05 *; < .01 **; < .001 ***

457

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Discussion

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In this study, we evaluated the potential of two listening effort tests (SWIRT and SVT) as an alternative for speech intelligibility tests in adult CI users. We expected that these tests would be able to show small differences in performance between different SNR conditions, however

462 speech intelligibility still appeared to be the most sensitive test. In this section, we will first dis-
463 cuss the results for each of the tests, followed by a general discussion.

464 **SRT50 scores**

465 SRT50 was measured for both the VU sentences used in SWIRT and the speech material
466 used in SVT to account for potential differences in intelligibility between speech materials. The
467 SRT50 scores for the different speech materials were significantly correlated, as expected. The
468 SRT50 scores show that there was a significant group difference of 1.1 dB between speech mate-
469 rials and that the speech material used in SVT was slightly more difficult to understand. This
470 could be related to the different structure, because the statements used in SVT have less context
471 than the regular sentences used in SWIRT. Alternatively, it could be related to the SVT material
472 having a male instead of a female talker. It is a small effect but should be taken into account
473 when comparing listening effort test methods with different speech materials to make sure that
474 they are measured at the same speech intelligibility performance level.

475 **Outliers in test items**

476 The SWIRT was conducted with Dutch sentences for the first time and therefore a thor-
477 ough analysis of potential outliers in the test lists and sentences was performed to gain insight
478 into test quality. In the SWIRT lists no outliers were identified. However, some words occurred
479 in multiple lists (e.g., ‘open’). Whether the word was a noun, verb, adjective, or other word had
480 no significant effect on the listening effort measured with SWIRT, but had a medium effect size
481 and could become significant with more data points. Future studies should therefore look further
482 into the effect of the word type. Perhaps the sentences in the created SWIRT lists should be rear-
483 ranged into new lists that have more equally occurring and memorable final words.

484 The Dutch SVT material was used earlier in other studies (Adank & Janse, 2009; Janse &
485 Adank, 2012; Pals et al., 2020), but a thorough analysis of the test material was lacking, so an
486 analysis to identify potential outliers was conducted as well. For some SVT items, the proportion
487 of trials answered correctly was significantly lower. This could be because a fact was not as
488 widely known as assumed (e.g., ‘parchment is made from leather’), or maybe the sentence was
489 pronounced less clearly than others. Since the SVT was not intended as a speech intelligibility
490 test, the intelligibility of the sentences was not controlled for.

491 Removing outliers in SVT items and rearranging SWIRT lists could improve the sensitiv-
492 ity of the tests somewhat.

493 **SVT**

494 For SVT, a significant effect of SNR condition on listening effort was found in the ex-
495 pected direction: a faster response, indicating less listening effort, for the condition with better
496 SNR. However, the mean difference in reaction time between SNR conditions was less than the
497 mean difference in reaction time between test and retest, and the standardized coefficients of the
498 GLMM for the SNR condition and test/retest were within each other’s 95% C.I. This indicates
499 that the SVT measure for listening effort had a low sensitivity to the SNR difference compared to
500 its accuracy. The significant interaction between test/retest and order indicates a potential learn-
501 ing effect, which lowers the accuracy of SVT. Pals et al. (2020) also found a decrease in reaction
502 time with SVT for consecutive test blocks in CI users. A training list with 10 sentences (five
503 true, five false) was used before the tests, but this did not seem to reduce the learning effect suffi-
504 ciently. An alternative explanation is that during the retest participants remembered some items
505 from the first test. Because items were selected randomly, some may have been repeated. We did
506 not think this would be an issue with one week in between test and retest, but it would be better

507 to avoid this in future tests. Analysis also showed that the false sentences were categorized cor-
508 rectly more often, but slower, than the true sentences. Moreover, sentences were categorized as
509 ‘false’ more often. A possible explanation is that when one or more words in the sentence are
510 misunderstood, it would probably be categorized as ‘false’, thus creating a slight bias towards the
511 ‘false’ category and a higher chance of false sentences being categorized correctly.

512 **SWIRT**

513 The outcomes of SWIRT showed a significant difference in listening effort and speech
514 intelligibility between the two SNR conditions in the expected direction: less listening effort and
515 better speech intelligibility for the condition with better SNR. For SWIRT, the mean difference
516 in listening effort between the SNR conditions was larger than the mean test-retest difference,
517 but the standardized coefficients of the GLMM for the SNR condition and test/retest were within
518 each other’s 95% C.I. In line with the results of Lunner et al. (2016), it was found that the last
519 item in the list was more easily remembered than the first and middle items. The mean difference
520 in speech intelligibility between the SNR conditions was also larger than the mean test-retest dif-
521 ference, and the standardized coefficient of the GLMM for the SNR condition was significantly
522 larger than the standardized coefficients of the other measures and of the test/retest condition.
523 This indicates that the SWIRT measure for listening effort had a low sensitivity to the SNR dif-
524 ference compared to its accuracy, but the sensitivity of the SWIRT measure for speech intelli-
525 bility was high compared to its accuracy. Moreover, the effect size of the SNR condition on the
526 SWIRT measure for speech intelligibility was higher than the effect size on the listening effort
527 measures.

528 **General discussion**

529 Whereas most previous studies focusing on listening effort included HA users, the cur-
530 rent study included CI users. Most CI users have a reduced ability to fully understand speech,
531 even in quiet. Some years ago, Ohlenforst et al. (2017) concluded from their literature review on
532 listening effort that there is scientific evidence from physiological methods suggesting that hear-
533 ing impairment leads to increased listening effort. Dingemanse & Goedegebure (2022) showed
534 that pupillometry measures indicated only a slight reduction in listening effort with increasing
535 SNR (for 50%, 70%, and near maximum speech intelligibility) in CI users. They compared their
536 findings with the findings of Zekveld et al. (2010; 2011) and found that the decrement in CI us-
537 ers was substantially smaller compared to the decrement found in normal-hearing listeners. The
538 results of Perreau et al. (2017) also showed that listening effort was reduced to a greater degree
539 for normal-hearing listeners compared to CI users with increasing SNR, using a dual-task para-
540 digm with a reaction time measure. But recently, in a study by Abdel-Latif & Meister (2022),
541 neither subjective (measured at 50% and 80% speech intelligibility) nor behavioral measures
542 (measured at 80% speech intelligibility) indicated a difference in listening effort between nor-
543 mal-hearing listeners and CI users. Abdel-Latif & Meister explain their different findings by the
544 underlying differences in psychometric functions of normal-hearing and CI users that were not
545 compensated for by Perreau et al. (2017) because SNR conditions were used instead of speech
546 intelligibility performance conditions. If it is true that listening effort follows the speech intelli-
547 gibility performance, it could also be that the minimum listening effort in CI users remains higher
548 than that of normal-hearing listeners if CI users are not able to reach 100% speech intelligibility.
549 This could explain the difference with the results from Dingemanse & Goedegebure (2022), who
550 included a near-maximum speech intelligibility condition where such a difference in minimum

551 listening effort would emerge. The smaller listening effort decrement per SNR increment and
552 higher minimum listening effort for CI users would make it harder to measure differences in lis-
553 tening effort in CI users compared to normal-hearing listeners. For hearing-aid users, compari-
554 sons of listening effort to normal-hearing listeners have been inconclusive (Ohlenforst et al.,
555 2017), and no studies with direct comparisons of listening effort in CI users and hearing-aid us-
556 ers were found.

557 The SNR conditions of $SRT50 + 4$ dB and $SRT50 + 8$ dB were chosen to be at relatively
558 high intelligibility, with an SNR difference that reflects an SNR reduction that an effective noise
559 reduction algorithm could achieve. The intelligibility difference between the conditions was nec-
560 essary to ensure a difference in listening effort. Because SNR conditions were used in the current
561 study, the intelligibility difference between the two conditions varies between participants, and
562 the listening effort difference may vary as well. However, since the conditions were chosen in
563 the range where the psychometric curve is flattening, this variation is minimal: the difference in
564 proportion of words correct between conditions would be at least 0.04 and at most 0.10 (Figure
565 1). Such a variation between CI users would also be present when comparing different hearing-
566 device settings. Of course, different hearing-device settings may cause differences that go be-
567 yond intelligibility, such as differences in sound quality, which can also affect listening effort.
568 For example, Pals et al. (2020) have shown that the number of active electrodes affects listening
569 effort in CI users. So, even though the SWIRT speech intelligibility measure was better able to
570 differentiate between the $SRT50 + 4$ dB and $SRT50 + 8$ dB conditions than the listening effort
571 measures, this may not be the case when comparing different hearing-device settings at a higher
572 intelligibility level. We do think that the difference in listening effort between the conditions in

573 the current study would be similar to the listening effort difference that can be expected from dif-
574 ferent hearing-device settings, since the 4 dB difference between conditions reflects the SNR re-
575 duction that an effective noise reduction algorithm could achieve (Brons et al., 2013). The test-
576 retest differences would become smaller when including more items/lists in SVT and SWIRT,
577 but the accompanying increment in measurement time would not be feasible in the clinic.

578 For both test methods included in the current study, the secondary task was auditory-re-
579 lated. A dual-task paradigm where the secondary task is not auditory-related, for example detect-
580 ing a visual stimulus such as the paradigm used by Desjardins & Doherty (2014), was not in-
581 cluded in the current study. It is still unclear which type of secondary task is most suited (Gagne
582 et al., 2017), so it would be good to compare listening effort tests with other types of secondary
583 tasks in future research.

584 **Conclusion**

585 This study explored whether it is feasible to measure listening effort differences due to
586 different input signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) in CI users using a sentence verification test (SVT)
587 and sentence final word identification and recall test (SWIRT), with the ultimate purpose of as-
588 sessing the feasibility to evaluate and compare different hearing-device settings in the clinic.
589 Moreover, the study investigated whether listening effort measures would be more suitable than
590 speech intelligibility measures.

591 Both SVT and SWIRT measured a significant difference in listening effort between the
592 two SNR conditions, so it is feasible to measure listening effort in CI users using these two be-
593 havioral tests. However, the effect of the SNR condition on the SVT and SWIRT listening effort
594 measures was similar in size compared to the test/retest difference. This means that a listening

617

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620

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